

Universität
Zürich ^{UZH}

Open Science Services

Secondary Publication

Legal Aspects

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What is secondary publication (or self-archiving)?

If researchers wish to make their scientific work publicly available, they can either do so in an open access publication venue (open access journal or open access book publisher) or self-archive their publication. For a secondary publication, authors publish their manuscript in a conventional publication venue and at the same time deposit the accepted manuscript or the already published version on a recognized repository.

Self-archiving or second publications constitute the so-called green road to Open Access. If researchers want to self-archive their publications, they need the appropriate rights.

What is copyright?

Authors as copyright holders of their own work generally grant publishers certain rights of use in their publishing contract so that the publisher can reproduce and process the work. Copyright holders can choose either to grant simple/non-exclusive or exclusive rights of use to the publisher. A simple right of use allows the work to be used in the approved manner, without excluding use by the authors themselves or by third parties. If researchers grant exclusive rights to their work, the publisher can use it to the exclusion of all other people.

Author rights and self-archiving: What you need to know

If authors do not publish directly in Open Access, they often grant the publisher exclusive rights. In most cases publishers allow self-archiving but authors must abide by the terms of the agreement, such as an embargo period or a predefined license. The requirements for self-archiving can be found either in the publisher's contract, on the publisher's website or in the Open Policy Finder by Jisc: <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk/>. Self-archiving publications on the UZH-repository ZORA requires researchers to take into account the conditions by the publisher (and the funding body). If anything is unclear, authors can reach out to the ZORA editorial team.

Retaining essential author rights?

In practice, there are three ways to retain rights as an author:

Adapt the publishing contract

In consultation with the publisher, adjustments can be made to the contract. For example, the accepted manuscript, which is identical in content to the published version but does not yet have the publisher's layout, can be explicitly excluded from the contract terms. Alternatively, certain expressions requiring the transfer of exclusive rights to the publisher can be deleted.

Attach an Open Access Addendum

Alternatively, authors can add an addendum to the contract that regulates the deposit of the publication in the repository. The addition must be countersigned by the publisher. Such an addendum can be generated online: <https://labs.creativecommons.org/scholars/>.

Apply the rights retention strategy of the SNSF

The Swiss National Science Foundation requires its grantees to publish the accepted manuscript version without an embargo period. The SNSF supports researchers in this with the Rights Retention Strategy. This entails that authors inform the publisher upon submission of their manuscript (e.g. in the footnotes of the manuscript) that they retain the rights to the accepted manuscript version and will publish it under a CC-BY license without an embargo period.

Applying licenses

When authors self-archive their publications in a repository, they usually have to apply a license. By sharing their publication with a license, authors can grant other persons certain rights of use to their work. The Creative Commons licenses are the most well-known licenses in that regard.

Inform yourself

Copyright and publishing contracts

For questions about publishing contracts and copyright, UZH members can contact the Open Science Services (oa@ub.uzh.ch) or the Team Legal Services and Data Protection (www.rud.uzh.ch).

University Library UZH

The website of the Open Science Services informs about legal aspects of publishing: <https://www.ub.uzh.ch/en/wissenschaftlich-arbeiten/Rechtliche-Aspekte/author-rights>

Institutional repository

UZH provides the institutional repository ZORA for secondary publications: www.zora.uzh.ch

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